

FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN ATTRACTING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENTS

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As a result of attracting foreign direct investments and their effective use, conditions are being created to ensure stable economic growth, create new jobs, and develop regions in the countries of the world.

The concept of foreign direct investments is comprehensive, and it is defined in the law “About investments and investment activities[1]”, published on December 25, 2019, on the basis of Decree № 598, as follows: “investments of a foreign investor at the expense of own funds or debt funds under risky conditions without government guarantees”. Foreign direct investment is very important for the market of developed and developing countries, because their companies need multinational financing and expertise to expand their international trade.

Paying attention to foreign experiences in attracting foreign investments, now the USA occupies one of the leading places in the world in terms of the volume of attracting foreign investments, that is, it makes up 20% of the total attracted investments worldwide. According to the 2023 information of CEIC DATA, which provides information on the economy and investment indicators of developed and developing countries, the amount of foreign direct investments attracted to the USA is 81.8 billion \$. The Committee on Foreign Investment in the United States (CFIUS) is the organization responsible for investigating the national security implications of foreign acquisitions or investments in US companies, and The United States can block or cancel such operations if it is identified as a threat to national security. CFIUS audits only cover acquisitions or investments involving the transfer of control of a US company to a foreign entity. Procedures for attracting foreign investment are regulated by the US government’s International Investment Survey Act of 1976, although each state has its own regulations on foreign direct investment [2].

Furthermore, one of the leaders in attracting foreign direct investments is the Republic of China. Not only the volume of the direct investments attracted in this country, but also the sector and how they are directed is essential. In addition, since 2001, China has been conducting “going-out” investment policy. At first, The Republic of China encouraged state-owned

enterprises to invest abroad, but in recent years, China's foreign investment has diversified, with state-owned and private enterprises investing in almost all industries and sectors of the economy. China is still one of the leaders in attracting foreign direct investment, and the total amount of foreign direct investment currently attracted is 33 billion US dollars as of 2023, compared to 2022, this indicator decreased by 80 % [3].

Foreign direct investment is an important mechanism for the development of economic growth in developing countries such as India. Basically, there are two routes for attracting foreign direct investment in this country, the first is the automatic route and the second route is the government. The automatic route does not require permission or authority from a private foreign investor, which means that it can invest in any company without government approval. In the second direction, no investment can be made without the prior approval of the Indian government [4].

In September 2022, the volume of foreign direct investment in Uzbekistan recorded an increase equal to 3,8 % of the country's nominal GDP (CEIC data, 2023). In 2023, the total cost in the country is 17,34 billion \$ projects are planned to be implemented, in which foreign investments will amount to 7.06 billion US dollars. It can be observed that the volume of foreign direct investments increased significantly between 2020 and 2022 (picture 1).

Picture 1. Foreign direct investments in Uzbekistan, in million US dollars

As can be seen from picture 1 above, the flow of foreign direct investment in Uzbekistan is increasing year by year, separately, it shows 1728 in 2020, 2276 in 2021, and 2531 in 2022. However, it should also be noted that in 2022 Greenfield investments, one of the forms of foreign direct investment (in which

the parent company starts an enterprise by building new operational facilities) decreased to 1221 mln US dollars from 3247 in 2020[5].

Based on the data above, it can be said that attracting profitable investments requires a clear and tailored strategy to increase attractiveness, develop a skilled workforce, invest in infrastructure and establish strong international relations.

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